

**CONGRUENCES FOR OVERPARTITION PAIRS AND 5 DOTS
BRACELET PARTITIONS MODULO 25**

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Abstract

Let $\overline{pp}(n)$ denote the number of overpartition pairs of n and $\mathfrak{B}_k(n)$ denote the number of k dots bracelet partitions of n . In this paper, we establish two infinite families of congruences modulo 25 for $\overline{pp}(n)$ and several congruences modulo 25 for $\mathfrak{B}_5(n)$. Moreover, we provide an elementary proof of two infinite families of congruences modulo 5 for $\overline{pp}(n)$, which was derived by Chen and Lin via modular forms.

1. Introduction

A *partition* [2] of a nonnegative integer n is a weakly decreasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is n . An *overpartition* [9] of n is a partition of n for which the first occurrence of a number may be overlined. In 2008, Bringmann and Lovejoy [6] introduced a rank for $\overline{pp}(n)$, the number of *overpartition pairs* of n , to investigate arithmetic properties of $\overline{pp}(n)$. The generating function of $\overline{pp}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{pp}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}^2}{(q; q)_{\infty}^2},$$

where here and in what follows, we adopt the following customary q -series notation:

$$(a; q)_{\infty} = \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n), \quad \text{for } |q| < 1.$$

Soon after, Keister, Sellers and Vary [17] as well as Kim [18] obtained congruences modulo powers of 2 for $\overline{pp}(n)$ via q -series arguments and modular forms. Later, Chen and Lin [7] further established a number of Ramanujan-type congruences modulo 3, 5 and 9 for $\overline{pp}(n)$. Recently, Xia [22] derived several new infinite families of congruences modulo 9 for $\overline{pp}(n)$. With the help of modular forms, Chen and Lin [7, Theorem 4.5] obtained the following two infinite families of congruences modulo 5:

Theorem 1.1. *For any $\alpha \geq 1$ and $n \geq 0$,*

$$\overline{pp}(5^\alpha(5n + 2)) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \tag{1}$$

$$\overline{pp}(5^\alpha(5n + 3)) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}. \tag{2}$$

In the process of studying broken 1-diamond partitions, Fu [13] introduced a generalization which he named *k dots bracelet partitions* and established various general congruences. Let $\mathfrak{B}_k(n)$ denote the number of *k dots bracelet partitions* of n . The generating function of $\mathfrak{B}_k(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_k(n)q^n = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}(q^k; q^k)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}^k (q^{2k}; q^{2k})_{\infty}}, \quad k \geq 3.$$

Using modular forms, Radu and Sellers [19, Theorem 1.4] established three congruences modulo squares of primes for $\mathfrak{B}_k(n)$. More precisely, they proved that

Theorem 1.2. *For any $n \geq 0$,*

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(10n + 7) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}, \tag{3}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_7(14n + 11) \equiv 0 \pmod{49}, \tag{4}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{11}(22n + 21) \equiv 0 \pmod{121}. \tag{5}$$

In a recent paper, Xia and Yao [23] obtained a number of congruences modulo small powers of 2 for $\mathfrak{B}_5(n)$. Other interesting arithmetic properties of $\mathfrak{B}_k(n)$ were subsequently found by many mathematicians, for example, [3, 10, 11, 12, 24].

The objective of this paper is to establish two infinite families of congruences modulo 25 for $\overline{pp}(n)$ and several congruences modulo 25 for $\mathfrak{B}_5(n)$. Moreover, we also provide an elementary proof of (1) and (2). Our main results are stated as follows:

Theorem 1.3. *For any $\alpha \geq 2$ and $n \geq 0$,*

$$\overline{pp}(4 \times 5^{\alpha+1}n + 11 \times 5^\alpha) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}, \tag{6}$$

$$\overline{pp}(4 \times 5^{\alpha+1}n + 19 \times 5^\alpha) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}. \tag{7}$$

Theorem 1.4. *For any $n \geq 0$,*

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(125n + 17) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}, \tag{8}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(125n + 67) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}, \tag{9}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(125n + 92) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}, \tag{10}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(125n + 117) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}, \tag{11}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(625n + 417) \equiv 0 \pmod{25}. \tag{12}$$

Theorem 1.5. *For any $n \geq 0$,*

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(12250n + 2042) \equiv \mathfrak{B}_5(1750n + 292) + 3\mathfrak{B}_5(250n + 42) \pmod{25}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(42250n + 7042) \equiv 2\mathfrak{B}_5(3250n + 542) + 2\mathfrak{B}_5(250n + 42) \pmod{25}. \quad (14)$$

The remainder of the paper is constructed as follows. In Sect. 2, we collect some necessary notation and lemmas. In Sect. 3, we give the proofs of Theorems 1.1 and 1.3. The proofs of Theorems 1.4 and 1.5 are presented in Sect. 4. We conclude in the last section with some remarks to motivate further investigation.

2. Preliminary Results

For notational convenience, denote

$$E_j = (q^j; q^j)_\infty.$$

Ramanujan’s general theta function is defined by

$$f(a, b) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{n(n+1)/2} b^{n(n-1)/2}, \quad |ab| < 1. \quad (15)$$

Two important special cases of (15) are [5, p. 36, Entry 22 (i) and (ii)]

$$\varphi(q) = f(q, q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = \frac{E_2^5}{E_1^2 E_4^2},$$

$$\psi(q) = f(q, q^3) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{(n^2+n)/2} = \frac{E_2^2}{E_1},$$

where the product representations arise from the Jacobi triple product identity [5, p. 35, Entry 19]

$$f(a, b) = (-a; ab)_\infty (-b; ab)_\infty (ab; ab)_\infty.$$

The following identity is due to Gauss [2, p. 23, Eq. (2.2.12)]:

$$\varphi(-q) = \frac{E_1^2}{E_2}.$$

First, we need the following identities involving $\varphi(q)$ and $\psi(q)$.

Lemma 2.1. *We have*

$$\psi(q) = f(q^{10}, q^{15}) + qf(q^5, q^{20}) + q^3\psi(q^{25}), \quad (16)$$

$$\varphi(q) = \varphi(q^{25}) + 2qf(q^{15}, q^{35}) + 2q^4f(q^5, q^{45}), \quad (17)$$

$$\varphi(q)^2 = \varphi(q^5)^2 + 4qf(q, q^9)f(q^3, q^7). \quad (18)$$

Proof. The identities (16)–(18) appear in [5, p. 262, Entry 10 (i), (ii) and (iv)], respectively. $\square$

We also require the following necessary lemmas.

Lemma 2.2. *We have*

$$\frac{1}{E_1^4} = \frac{E_{10}^2}{E_2^2 E_5^4} + 4q \frac{E_{10}^5}{E_1^3 E_2 E_5^5}, \tag{19}$$

$$\frac{E_2^5}{E_1^5} = \frac{E_{10}}{E_5} + 5q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^4}{E_1^3 E_5^2}. \tag{20}$$

Proof. Equations (19) and (20) follow from [4, Eqs. (2.6) and (2.29)]. $\square$

Lemma 2.3. *We have*

$$\frac{E_1}{E_{25}} = \frac{1}{R(q^5)} - q - q^2 R(q^5), \tag{21}$$

$$\frac{E_5^6}{E_{25}^6} = \frac{1}{R(q^5)^5} - 11q^5 - q^{10} R(q^5)^5, \tag{22}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{E_1} = \frac{E_{25}^5}{E_5^6} & \left(\frac{1}{R(q^5)^4} + \frac{q}{R(q^5)^3} + \frac{2q^2}{R(q^5)^2} + \frac{3q^3}{R(q^5)} + 5q^4 \right. \\ & \left. - 3q^5 R(q^5) + 2q^6 R(q^5)^2 - q^7 R(q^5)^3 + q^8 R(q^5)^4 \right), \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

where

$$R(q) = \frac{(q; q^5)_\infty (q^4; q^5)_\infty}{(q^2; q^5)_\infty (q^3; q^5)_\infty}.$$

Proof. The identities (21)–(23) appear in [15, Eqs. (8.4.1), (8.4.2) and (8.4.4)]. $\square$

Lemma 2.4. *Let $x = \frac{1}{R(q)}$, $y = \frac{1}{R(q^2)}$ and $K = \frac{E_2 E_5^5}{E_1 E_{10}^5}$. For $\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and $\beta \in \mathbb{Z}$, define*

$$P(\alpha, \beta) = x^{\alpha+2\beta} y^{2\alpha-\beta} + \frac{(-1)^{\alpha+\beta} q^{2\alpha}}{x^{\alpha+2\beta} y^{2\alpha-\beta}}. \tag{24}$$

Then

$$P(\alpha, \beta + 1) = \frac{4q}{K} P(\alpha, \beta) + P(\alpha, \beta - 1), \tag{25}$$

$$P(\alpha + 2, 0) = K P(\alpha + 1, 0) + q^2 P(\alpha, 0), \tag{26}$$

$$P(\alpha + 2, -1) = \left(K - 2q + \frac{4q^2}{K} \right) P(\alpha + 1, 0) - q^2 P(\alpha, 1). \tag{27}$$

where

$$P(0, 0) = 2,$$

$$P(0, 1) = \frac{x^2}{y} - \frac{y}{x^2} = \frac{4q}{K}, \tag{28}$$

$$P(1, 0) = xy^2 - \frac{q^2}{xy^2} = K, \tag{29}$$

$$P(1, -1) = \frac{y^3}{x} + \frac{q^2x}{y^3} = K - 2q + \frac{4q^2}{K}. \tag{30}$$

Proof. Equations (25)–(27) are proved in [8, Theorem 1.1]. The identities (28)–(30) appear in [4, Lemma 1.3]. □

Now we introduce an operator H modulo 13, given by

$$H \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_{13n} q^{13n}.$$

Hirschhorn [16] proved that

Lemma 2.5. *If $\eta = \frac{E_1}{q^7 E_{169}}$ and $T = \frac{E_{13}^2}{q^{13} E_{169}^2}$, then*

$$H(\eta^4) = 2T^2 - 13. \tag{31}$$

According to the binomial theorem, we can easily obtain the following congruence, which will be frequently used without explicit mention.

Lemma 2.6. *If p is a prime, then*

$$(q; q)_{\infty}^p \equiv (q^p; q^p)_{\infty} \pmod{p}.$$

3. Proofs of Theorems 1.1 and 1.3

First, we prove (1) and (2).

In view of (17), we obtain, modulo 5,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{pp}(n)q^n &= \frac{E_2^2}{E_1^4} = \frac{1}{\varphi(-q)^2} = \frac{\varphi(-q)^3}{\varphi(-q)^5} \equiv \frac{\varphi(-q)^3}{\varphi(-q^5)} \\ &= \frac{1}{\varphi(-q^5)} \left(\varphi(-q^{25}) - 2qf(-q^{15}, -q^{35}) + 2q^4 f(-q^5, -q^{45}) \right)^3 \\ &= \frac{1}{\varphi(-q^5)} \left(\varphi(-q^{25})^3 - 6q\varphi(-q^{25})^2 f(-q^{15}, -q^{35}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 12q^2 \varphi(-q^{25}) f(-q^{15}, -q^{35})^2 - 8q^3 f(-q^{15}, -q^{35})^3 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 6q^4 \varphi(-q^{25})^2 f(-q^5, -q^{45}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -24q^5\varphi(-q^{25})f(-q^{15}, -q^{35})f(-q^5, -q^{45}) \\
 & + 24q^6f(-q^{15}, -q^{35})^2f(-q^5, -q^{45}) + 12q^8\varphi(-q^{25})f(-q^5, -q^{45})^2 \\
 & - 24q^9f(-q^{15}, -q^{35})f(-q^5, -q^{45})^2 + 8q^{12}f(-q^5, -q^{45})^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{pp}(5n)q^{5n} \equiv \frac{\varphi(-q^{25})^3 - 4q^5\varphi(-q^{25})f(-q^{15}, -q^{35})f(-q^5, -q^{45})}{\varphi(-q^5)}.$$

Therefore, by (18), we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{pp}(5n)q^n & \equiv \frac{\varphi(-q^5)(\varphi(-q^5)^2 - 4qf(-q^3, -q^7)f(-q, -q^9))}{\varphi(-q)} \\
 & = \frac{\varphi(-q^5)\varphi(-q)^2}{\varphi(-q)} = \varphi(-q)\varphi(-q^5) \\
 & = \varphi(-q^5)(\varphi(-q^{25}) - 2qf(-q^{15}, -q^{35}) + 2q^4f(-q^5, -q^{45})).
 \end{aligned}$$

By induction, we easily deduce that for $\alpha \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{pp}(5^\alpha n)q^n & \equiv \varphi(-q)\varphi(-q^5) \\
 & = \varphi(-q^5)(\varphi(-q^{25}) - 2qf(-q^{15}, -q^{35}) + 2q^4f(-q^5, -q^{45})). \quad (32)
 \end{aligned}$$

It follows easily that there are no term on the right hand side of (32) in which the powers of q is congruent to 2 or 3 modulo 5, i.e.,

$$\overline{pp}(5^\alpha(5n + 2)) \equiv \overline{pp}(5^\alpha(5n + 3)) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

This proves (1) and (2).

We are now in a position to prove (6) and (7).

According to [7] and (20), we obtain, (all the following congruences are modulo 25 in the sequel unless otherwise specified)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{pp}(4n + 3) & = 32 \frac{E_2^{20}}{E_1^{22}} = 32 \frac{1}{E_1^2} \left(\frac{E_{10}}{E_5} + 5q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^4}{E_1^3 E_5^2} \right)^4 \quad (33) \\
 & = 32 \frac{E_{10}^4}{E_1^2 E_5^4} + 640q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^7}{E_1^5 E_5^5} + 4800q^2 \frac{E_2^2 E_{10}^{10}}{E_1^8 E_5^6} \\
 & \quad + 16000q^3 \frac{E_2^3 E_{10}^{13}}{E_1^{11} E_5^7} + 20000q^4 \frac{E_2^4 E_{10}^{16}}{E_1^{14} E_5^8} \\
 & \equiv 32 \frac{E_{10}^4}{E_1^2 E_5^4} + 640q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^7}{E_1^5 E_5^5}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Define

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_1(n)q^n = \frac{E_{10}^4}{E_1^2 E_5^4}, \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_2(n)q^n = 20q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^7}{E_1^5 E_5^5}.$$

To obtain (6) and (7), we need to prove that for any $\alpha \geq 2$,

$$g_1 \left(5^{\alpha+1}n + \frac{11 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) \equiv g_1 \left(5^{\alpha+1}n + \frac{19 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) \equiv 0, \tag{34}$$

$$g_2 \left(5^{\alpha+1}n + \frac{11 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) \equiv g_2 \left(5^{\alpha+1}n + \frac{19 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) \equiv 0. \tag{35}$$

With the help of (23), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_1(n)q^n &= \frac{E_{10}^4 E_{25}^{10}}{E_5^{16}} \left(\frac{1}{R(q^5)^4} + \frac{q}{R(q^5)^3} + \frac{2q^2}{R(q^5)^2} + \frac{3q^3}{R(q^5)} + 5q^4 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 3q^5 R(q^5) + 2q^6 R(q^5)^2 - q^7 R(q^5)^3 + q^8 R(q^5)^4 \right)^2 \\ &= \frac{E_{10}^4 E_{25}^{10}}{E_5^{16}} \left(\frac{1}{R(q^5)^8} + \frac{2q}{R(q^5)^7} + \frac{5q^2}{R(q^5)^6} + \frac{10q^3}{R(q^5)^5} + \frac{20q^4}{R(q^5)^4} \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{16q^5}{R(q^5)^3} + \frac{27q^6}{R(q^5)^2} + \frac{20q^7}{R(q^5)} + 15q^8 - 20q^9 R(q^5) \\ &\quad + 27q^{10} R(q^5)^2 - 16q^{11} R(q^5)^3 + 20q^{12} R(q^5)^4 \\ &\quad \left. - 10q^{13} R(q^5)^5 + 5q^{14} R(q^5)^6 - 2q^{15} R(q^5)^7 + q^{16} R(q^5)^8 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Picking out these terms of the form q^{5n+3} and applying (22),

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_1(5n+3)q^n &= 10 \frac{E_2^4 E_5^4}{E_1^{10}} + 125q \frac{E_2^4 E_5^{10}}{E_1^{16}} \equiv 10 \frac{E_2^4 E_5^4}{E_1^{10}} \\ &\equiv 10 E_5^2 E_{50}^4 \left(\frac{1}{R(q^{10})} - q^2 - q^4 R(q^{10}) \right)^4 \\ &= 10 E_5^2 E_{50}^4 \left(\frac{1}{R(q^{10})^4} - \frac{4q^2}{R(q^{10})^3} + \frac{2q^4}{R(q^{10})^2} \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{8q^6}{R(q^{10})} - 5q^8 - 8q^{10} R(q^{10}) + 2q^{12} R(q^{10})^2 \\ &\quad \left. + 4q^{14} R(q^{10})^3 + q^{16} R(q^{10})^4 \right), \end{aligned}$$

from which we obtain

$$g_1(25n+18) \equiv 0,$$

which is what we wanted to prove. But note that we obtained a stronger result for (34).

According to (21), we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_2(n)q^n \equiv 20q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^7}{E_5^6} = 20q \frac{E_{10}^7 E_{50}}{E_5^6} \left(\frac{1}{R(q^{10})} - q^2 - q^4 R(q^{10}) \right).$$

In view of (16),

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_2(5n+3)q^n &\equiv -20 \frac{E_2^7 E_{10}}{E_1^6} \equiv -20 \frac{E_2^2 E_{10}^2}{E_1 E_5} = -20\psi(q)\psi(q^5) \\ &= -20\psi(q^5) (f(q^{10}, q^{15}) + qf(q^5, q^{20}) + q^3\psi(q^{25})), \end{aligned}$$

from which we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_2(25n+18)q^n &\equiv -20\psi(q)\psi(q^5) \\ &= -20\psi(q^5) (f(q^{10}, q^{15}) + qf(q^5, q^{20}) + q^3\psi(q^{25})). \end{aligned}$$

By induction, we find that for $\alpha \geq 2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} g_2 \left(5^\alpha n + \frac{3 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) q^n &\equiv -20\psi(q)\psi(q^5) \\ &= -20\psi(q^5) (f(q^{10}, q^{15}) + qf(q^5, q^{20}) + q^3\psi(q^{25})). \end{aligned}$$

Since there are no term on the right hand side in which the powers of q is congruent to 2 or 4 modulo 5, we obtain that for any $\alpha \geq 2$,

$$g_2 \left(5^{\alpha+1}n + \frac{11 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) \equiv g_2 \left(5^{\alpha+1}n + \frac{19 \times 5^\alpha - 3}{4} \right) \equiv 0,$$

as required.

The congruences (6) and (7) are immediate consequences of (33)–(35).

Remark 3.1. According to (33), one easily obtains

$$\overline{pp}(4n+3) \equiv 0 \pmod{32}. \tag{36}$$

The congruence (36) together with (6) and (7) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{pp} (4 \times 5^{\alpha+1}n + 11 \times 5^\alpha) &\equiv 0 \pmod{800}, \\ \overline{pp} (4 \times 5^{\alpha+1}n + 19 \times 5^\alpha) &\equiv 0 \pmod{800}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha \geq 2$.

4. Proof of Theorems 1.4 and 1.5

We first prove (8)–(12).

By (21) and (23), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(n)q^n &= \frac{E_2 E_5}{E_1^5 E_{10}} \\ &= \frac{E_5^{25} E_{50}}{E_5^{29} E_{10}} \left(\frac{1}{R(q^5)^4} + \frac{q}{R(q^5)^3} + \frac{2q^2}{R(q^5)^2} + \frac{3q^3}{R(q^5)} + 5q^4 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 3q^5 R(q^5) + 2q^6 R(q^5)^2 - q^7 R(q^5)^3 + q^8 R(q^5)^4 \right)^5 \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{1}{R(q^{10})} - q^2 - q^4 R(q^{10}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Extracting all terms of the form q^{5n+2} , dividing by q^2 , replacing q^5 by q , and using (24)–(27), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(5n+2)q^n &= \frac{E_5^{25} E_{10}}{E_1^{29} E_2} \left((20P(4,7) - P(4,8)) \right. \\ &\quad + q(2030P(3,5) - 456P(3,6) - 65P(3,7)) \\ &\quad + q^2(15680P(2,3) - 9222P(2,4) - 3710P(2,5)) \\ &\quad + q^3(9350P(1,1) - 15433P(1,2) - 17185P(1,3)) \\ &\quad \left. + q^4(-11945 - 11200P(0,1)) \right) \\ &= \frac{E_5^{25} E_{10}}{E_1^{29} E_2} \left(19K^4 + 1773qK^3 + 18574q^2K^2 + 36105q^3K \right. \\ &\quad - 106995q^4 - \frac{788152q^5}{K} - \frac{2381104q^6}{K^2} \\ &\quad - \frac{4837312q^7}{K^3} - \frac{6481920q^8}{K^4} - \frac{5534720q^9}{K^5} \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{2973696q^{10}}{K^6} - \frac{868352q^{11}}{K^7} - \frac{65536q^{12}}{K^8} \right). \end{aligned}$$

By virtue of (19), after simplification, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(5n+2)q^n &= 19 \frac{E_1^{15} E_5^5}{E_2^{21} E_5^3} + 2685q \frac{E_1^{12} E_{10}^8}{E_2^{20} E_5^4} + 116650q^2 \frac{E_1^9 E_{10}^{11}}{E_2^{19} E_5^5} \\ &\quad + 2606825q^3 \frac{E_1^6 E_{10}^{14}}{E_2^{18} E_5^6} + 35696625q^4 \frac{E_1^3 E_{10}^{17}}{E_2^{17} E_5^7} \\ &\quad + 324425000q^5 \frac{E_{10}^{20}}{E_2^{16} E_5^8} + 2030950000q^6 \frac{E_{10}^{23}}{E_1^3 E_2^{15} E_5^9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ 8849000000q^7 \frac{E_{10}^{26}}{E_1^6 E_2^{14} E_5^{10}} + 26480000000q^8 \frac{E_{10}^{29}}{E_1^9 E_2^{13} E_5^{11}} \\
 &+ 52080000000q^9 \frac{E_{10}^{32}}{E_1^{12} E_2^{12} E_5^{12}} + 60800000000q^{10} \frac{E_{10}^{35}}{E_1^{15} E_2^{11} E_5^{13}} \\
 &+ 32000000000q^{11} \frac{E_{10}^{38}}{E_1^{18} E_2^{10} E_5^{14}}, \tag{37}
 \end{aligned}$$

from which we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(5n + 2)q^n \equiv 19 \frac{E_1^{15} E_{10}^5}{E_2^{21} E_5^3} + 10q \frac{E_1^{12} E_{10}^8}{E_2^{20} E_5^4}. \tag{38}$$

Plugging (20) into (38) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(5n + 2)q^n &\equiv 19 \frac{E_2^4 E_5^2}{E_1^{10}} + 10q \frac{E_1^{12} E_{10}^8}{E_2^{20} E_5^4} \\
 &\equiv 19 \frac{E_5^2}{E_2^6} \left(\frac{E_{10}}{E_5} + 5q \frac{E_2 E_{10}^4}{E_1^3 E_5^2} \right)^2 + 10q \frac{E_{10}^5}{E_1^3 E_2^5 E_5} \\
 &= 19 \frac{E_{10}^2}{E_2^6} + \left(190q \frac{E_{10}^5}{E_1^3 E_2^5 E_5} + 10q \frac{E_{10}^5}{E_1^3 E_2^5 E_5} \right) + 475q^2 \frac{E_{10}^8}{E_1^6 E_2^4 E_5^2} \\
 &\equiv 19 \frac{E_{10}^2}{E_2^6} = 19 \frac{E_{50}^{30}}{E_{10}^{34}} \left(\frac{1}{R(q^{10})^4} + \frac{q^2}{R(q^{10})^3} + \frac{2q^4}{R(q^{10})^2} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{3q^6}{R(q^{10})} + 5q^8 - 3q^{10} R(q^{10}) + 2q^{12} R(q^{10})^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - q^{14} R(q^{10})^3 + q^{16} R(q^{10})^4 \right)^6. \tag{39}
 \end{aligned}$$

Picking out these terms of the form q^{5n+3} as well as utilizing (21) and (22),

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(25n + 17)q^n &\equiv 5985q \frac{E_{10}^6}{E_2^{10}} + 617500q^3 \frac{E_{10}^{12}}{E_2^{16}} + 3740625q^5 \frac{E_{10}^{18}}{E_2^{22}} \\
 &\quad + 222656250q^7 \frac{E_{10}^{24}}{E_2^{28}} + 927734375q^9 \frac{E_{10}^{30}}{E_2^{34}} \\
 &\equiv 10q \frac{E_{10}^6}{E_2^{10}} \equiv 10qE_{10}^4. \tag{40}
 \end{aligned}$$

Notice that all terms in the right hand side of (40) are of the form q^{5n+1} , therefore we deduce that

$$\mathfrak{B}_5(25(5n + r) + 17) \equiv 0, \quad r \in \{0, 2, 3, 4\}.$$

This proves (8)–(11).

Furthermore, it follows from (40) that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(125n + 42)q^n &\equiv 10E_2^4 \equiv 10\frac{E_{10}}{E_2} \\ &= 10\frac{E_{50}^5}{E_{10}^5} \left(\frac{1}{R(q^{10})^4} + \frac{q^2}{R(q^{10})^3} + \frac{2q^4}{R(q^{10})^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{3q^6}{R(q^{10})} + 5q^8 - 3q^{10}R(q^{10}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2q^{12}R(q^{10})^2 - q^{14}R(q^{10})^3 + q^{16}R(q^{10})^4 \right), \end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

from which we obtain (12).

Finally, we present the proofs of (13) and (14).

It follows immediately from (41) that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(250n + 42)q^n \equiv 10\frac{E_5}{E_1} = 10 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(n)q^n. \tag{42}$$

In [1], Ahmed and Baruah proved that

$$5b_5(49n + 8) \equiv 5b_5(7n + 1) + 15b_5(n), \tag{43}$$

The congruence (13) follows from (42) together with (43).

By (42), one sees that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(250n + 42)q^{n+11} \equiv 10q^{11}E_1^4 = 10q^{39}E_{169}^4\eta^4.$$

Applying the H operator to both side of the above congruence and using (31), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(3250n + 542)q^{13n+13} \equiv 10q^{39}E_{169}^4H(\eta^4) = 10q^{39}E_{169}^4(2T^2 - 13).$$

Namely,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(3250n + 542)q^n &\equiv 10q^2E_{13}^4 \left(\frac{2E_1^4}{q^2E_{13}^4} - 13 \right) \equiv 20\frac{E_5}{E_1} + 20q^2\frac{E_{65}}{E_{13}} \\ &= 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(250n + 42)q^n + 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_5(250n + 42)q^{13n+2}. \end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

The congruence (14) is an immediate consequence of (44).

5. Closing Remarks

We conclude with several remarks that merit further investigation.

- 1) From (39), we readily obtain (3). From this perspective, we provide an elementary proof of (3). It would be interesting to find an elementary proof of (4) and (5).
- 2) In [21], Wang obtained arithmetic properties for overpartition triple function $\bar{p}_3(n)$ modulo 7, 9, 11 and small powers of 2, where

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_3(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}^3}{(q; q)_{\infty}^3} = \frac{1}{\varphi(-q)^3}.$$

Following the similar strategy of proving (1) and (2) and utilizing the generating function of $\bar{p}(5n)$ [14, 20] ($\bar{p}(n)$ denotes the number of overpartitions of n), we can prove that for any $\alpha \geq 1$,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_3(5^{2\alpha}n)q^n \equiv \varphi(-q^5) \pmod{5}, \tag{45}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_3(5^{2\alpha+1}n)q^n \equiv \varphi(-q) \pmod{5}. \tag{46}$$

The congruences (45) and (46) together with (17) imply that for any $\alpha \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{p}_3(5^{\alpha+1}(5n+2)) &\equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ \bar{p}_3(5^{\alpha+1}(5n+3)) &\equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ \bar{p}_3(5^{2\alpha}(5n+1)) &\equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ \bar{p}_3(5^{2\alpha}(5n+4)) &\equiv 0 \pmod{5}. \end{aligned}$$

- 3) Similar to (37), we can also obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}\bar{p}(5n)q^n &= \frac{E_1^{12}E_{10}^2}{E_2^{16}} + 180q \frac{E_1^9E_{10}^5}{E_2^{15}E_5} + 6150q^2 \frac{E_1^6E_{10}^8}{E_2^{14}E_5^2} \\ &+ 96500q^3 \frac{E_1^3E_{10}^{11}}{E_2^{13}E_5^3} + 852625q^4 \frac{E_{10}^{14}}{E_2^{12}E_5^4} \\ &+ 4540000q^5 \frac{E_{10}^{17}}{E_1^3E_2^{11}E_5^5} + 14550000q^6 \frac{E_{10}^{20}}{E_1^6E_2^{10}E_5^6} \\ &+ 26000000q^7 \frac{E_{10}^{23}}{E_1^9E_2^9E_5^7} + 20000000q^8 \frac{E_{10}^{26}}{E_1^{12}E_2^8E_5^8} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_3(5n)q^n &= \frac{E_1^{22}E_{10}^5}{E_2^{26}E_5^4} + 646q \frac{E_1^{19}E_{10}^8}{E_2^{25}E_5^5} + 48855q^2 \frac{E_1^{16}E_{10}^{11}}{E_2^{24}E_5^6} \\ &+ 1659900q^3 \frac{E_1^{13}E_{10}^{14}}{E_2^{23}E_5^7} + 33135375q^4 \frac{E_1^{10}E_{10}^{17}}{E_2^{22}E_5^8} \\ &+ 435633750q^5 \frac{E_1^7E_{10}^{20}}{E_2^{21}E_5^9} + 3997615625q^6 \frac{E_1^4E_{10}^{23}}{E_2^{20}E_5^{10}} \\ &+ 26374325000q^7 \frac{E_1E_{10}^{26}}{E_2^{19}E_5^{11}} + 126474750000q^8 \frac{E_{10}^{29}}{E_1^2E_2^{18}E_5^{12}} \\ &+ 438625000000q^9 \frac{E_{10}^{32}}{E_1^5E_2^{17}E_5^{13}} + 1075000000000q^{10} \frac{E_{10}^{35}}{E_1^8E_2^{16}E_5^{14}} \\ &+ 1770000000000q^{11} \frac{E_{10}^{38}}{E_1^{11}E_2^{15}E_5^{15}} + 1760000000000q^{12} \frac{E_{10}^{41}}{E_1^{14}E_2^{14}E_5^{16}} \\ &+ 800000000000q^{13} \frac{E_{10}^{44}}{E_1^{17}E_2^{13}E_5^{17}}. \end{aligned}$$

- 4) It seems that there are no congruences modulo 49 for $\mathfrak{B}_7(n)$ and congruences modulo 121 for $\mathfrak{B}_{11}(n)$ similar to (8)–(11) with the help of a computer. That is, there are no integers $1 \leq i \leq 342$ and $1 \leq j \leq 1330$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{B}_7(343n + i) &\equiv 0 \pmod{49}, \\ \mathfrak{B}_{11}(1331n + j) &\equiv 0 \pmod{121}. \end{aligned}$$

It is worth mentioning that Radu and Sellers [19] conjectured the following infinite family of congruences modulo powers of 7 for $\mathfrak{B}_7(n)$.

Conjecture 5.1. For any $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 0$,

$$\mathfrak{B}_7\left(7^\alpha n + \frac{7^\alpha + 1}{2}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{7^{\lceil \frac{\alpha-1}{2} \rceil}}.$$

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References

- [1] Z. Ahmed and N. D. Baruah, New congruences for ℓ -regular partitions for $\ell \in \{5, 6, 7, 49\}$, *Ramanujan J.* **40** (2016), 649–668.
- [2] G. E. Andrews, *The Theory of Partitions*, Encyclopedia of Mathematics and Its Applications, Vol. 2 (G.-C. Rota, ed.), Addison-Wesley, Reading, 1976 (Reprinted: Cambridge Univ. Press, London and New York, 1984).
- [3] N. D. Baruah and Z. Ahmed, Congruences modulo p^2 and p^3 for k dots bracelet partitions with $k = mp^s$, *J. Number Theory* **151** (2015), 129–146.
- [4] N. D. Baruah and N. M. Begum, Exact generating functions for the number of partitions into distinct parts, *Int. J. Number Theory* **14** (2018), 1995–2011.
- [5] B. C. Berndt, *Ramanujan's Notebooks, Part III*, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1991.
- [6] K. Bringmann and J. Lovejoy, Rank and congruences for overpartition pairs, *Int. J. Number Theory* **4** (2008), 303–322.
- [7] W. Y. C. Chen and B. L. S. Lin, Arithmetic properties of overpartition pairs, *Acta Arith.* **151** (2012), 263–277.
- [8] S. Chern and D. Tang, Representations involving the Rogers–Ramanujan continued fraction and their applications, submitted.
- [9] S. Corteel and J. Lovejoy, Overpartitions, *Trans. Amer. Math. Soc.* **356** (2004), 1623–1635.
- [10] S. Cui and N. S. S. Gu, Congruences for k dots bracelet partition functions, *Int. J. Number Theory* **9** (2013), 1885–1894.
- [11] S. Cui and N. S. S. Gu, Congruences for broken 3-diamond and 7 dots bracelet partitions, *Ramanujan J.* **35** (2014), 165–178.
- [12] S. Cui, N. S. S. Gu and A. X. Huang, Congruence properties for a certain kind of partition functions, *Adv. Math.* **290** (2016), 739–772.
- [13] S. Fu, Combinatorial proof of one congruence for the broken 1-diamond partition and a generalization, *Int. J. Number Theory* **7** (2011), 133–144.
- [14] C. Gu, M. D. Hirschhorn, J. A. Sellers and E. X. W. Xia, Infinite families of congruences modulo 5 and 9 for overpartitions, *Bull. Pol. Acad. Sci. Math.* **66** (2018), 31–44.
- [15] M. D. Hirschhorn, *The Power of q* , Developments in Mathematics Vol. 49, Springer, Cham, 2017.
- [16] M. D. Hirschhorn, Ramanujan's tau function, in: *Analytic Number Theory, Modular Forms and q -Hypergeometric Series*, 311–328, Springer Proc. Math. Stat., 221, Springer, Cham, 2017.
- [17] D. Keister, J. Sellers and R. Vary, Some arithmetic properties of overpartition k -tuples, *Integers* **9** (2009) Article A17.
- [18] B. Kim, Overpartition pairs modulo powers of 2, *Discrete Math.* **311** (2011), 835–840.
- [19] C. S. Radu and J. A. Sellers, Congruences modulo squares of primes for Fu's k dots bracelet partitions, *Int. J. Number Theory* **9** (2013), 939–943.
- [20] S. Treneer, Congruences for the coefficients of weakly holomorphic modular forms, *Proc. London Math. Soc. (3)* **93** (2006), 304–324.
- [21] L. Wang, Arithmetic properties of overpartition triples, *Acta Math. Sin. (Engl. Ser.)* **33** (2017), 37–50.
- [22] E. X. W. Xia, New infinite families of Ramanujan-type congruences modulo 9 for overpartition pairs, *Colloq. Math.* **140** (2015), 91–105.
- [23] E. X. W. Xia and O. X. M. Yao, Congruences modulo powers of 2 for Fu's 5 dots bracelet partitions, *Bull. Aust. Math. Soc.* **89** (2014), 360–372.
- [24] O. X. M. Yao, Arithmetic properties for Fu's 9 dots bracelet partitions, *Int. J. Number Theory* **11** (2015), 1063–1072.